

SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN'S NUTRITIONAL STATUS

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Abstract. *The nutritional status of school-aged children impacts their health, cognition, and subsequently their educational achievement. The school is an opportune setting to provide health and nutrition services to disadvantaged children. Yet, school-aged children are not commonly included in health and nutrition surveys. An up-to-date overview of their nutritional status across the world is not available. The purpose of this study is to provide a summary of the recent data on the nutritional status of school-aged children in developing countries and countries in transition and identify issues of public health concern.*

Keywords: *dietary intake, nutritional risk factors, living condition.*

Relevance. The available data indicate that the nutritional status of school-aged children in the reviewed regions are considerably inadequate. Underweight and thinness were most prominent in populations from South-East Asia and Africa, whereas in Latin America the prevalence of underweight or thinness was generally below 10%. More than half of the studies on anemia reported moderate (> 20%) or severe (> 40%) prevalence of anemia. Prevalences of 20% to 30% were commonly reported for deficiencies of iron, iodine, zinc, and vitamin A. The prevalence of overweight was highest in Latin American countries (20% to 35%). In Africa, Asia, and the Eastern Mediterranean, the prevalence of overweight was generally below 15%. The available data indicate that malnutrition is a public health issue in school-aged children in developing countries and countries in transition. However, the available data, especially data on micronutrient status, are limited. These findings emphasize the need for nutrition interventions in school-aged children and more high-quality research to assess nutritional status in this age group.

The purpose of this study. Thus, the purpose of this study was to determine the nutrition and health status of internally displaced schoolchildren in the Western and Southern regions of Uzbekistan through a joint baseline survey.

Materials and methods of research. Undernutrition, typified by an insufficient nutrient intake and limited access to nourishing foods, remains a critical concern in various regions. This silent crisis manifests in forms like stunting, wasting, and micronutrient deficiencies, impacting children's susceptibility to infections, physical and cognitive development, and elevating the risk of morbidity and mortality. Stunting, a consequence of chronic undernutrition, not only hampers physical growth but also compromises cognitive function, educational achievement, and future economic productivity. Overnutrition refers to a condition in which an individual consumes more calories than their body requires for energy expenditure and metabolic functions. This often leads to weight gain and can result in various health issues such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and metabolic disorders. Thus, overnutrition among school-age children in developing nations, manifests as conditions such as overweight and obesity, stemming from the consumption of excess calories, unbalanced dietary patterns, and sedentary behaviors. This dietary imbalance exacerbates health concerns and underscores the urgent need for comprehensive interventions addressing both dietary habits and lifestyle choices. Furthermore, malnutrition in overweight individuals underscores the complexity of nutritional status, as excess weight does not necessarily

equate to an adequate intake of essential nutrients, often masking underlying deficiencies and posing additional health risks. This dual burden of malnutrition, with coexisting undernourished and over-nourished individuals, further complicates the global health landscape. Overnutrition-related non-communicable diseases have emerged as significant threats among children and adolescents, emphasizing the urgency of addressing this issue. Biochemical assessment uses laboratory measurements of serum protein, serum micronutrient levels, serum lipids, and immunological parameters to assess general nutritional status and to identify specific nutritional deficiencies. Specific laboratory tests most frequently used include measurements of albumin, prealbumin, hemoglobin, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity, magnesium, vitamin levels, trace elements, cholesterol, triglycerides, fasting glucose, CD4, CD8, virus load of HIV, renal function, and liver enzyme levels.

Clinical assessment includes a medical history and a physical examination to identify signs of or contributors to malnutrition. Key areas in the clinical assessment include physical appearance, evaluation of opportunistic infections and comorbid conditions, occurrence of diarrhea, symptoms of gastrointestinal distress or malabsorption, medications, use of nutritional or herbal supplements, and functional status. Assessment of social, psychological, and financial resources that may affect an individual's ability to obtain, prepare, and eat food are as important as the medical assessment in evaluating nutritional risk factors.

The dietary intake component of the nutritional assessment examines adequacy of the current diet for micronutrient as well as macronutrient composition, identifies factors affecting adequate intake, and identifies food intolerances that may affect intake and proper medication regimens. It is the goal of dietary assessment and subsequent education and counseling to prevent loss of weight and lean body mass and to determine measures that may improve the overall health of a patient. Both 24-h recall and diet history have been shown to provide good estimates of dietary intake for a baseline assessment; these methods compare favorably with weighed food records and food frequency questionnaires.

Biochemical assessment in children includes laboratory measurements similar to those used for adults. The nutritional implications of laboratory values must be considered in the context of other parameters of the nutritional assessment. Clinical assessment parameters specific to children include detailed medical history and physical examination. Special attention is paid to the presence of gastrointestinal disease or opportunistic infections that affect nutritional health, medications, dental health, developmental assessment, neurological disease, and behavioral issues. With infants, it is important to consider perinatal factors such as nutrition of the mother, exposure to drugs or alcohol, birth weight, and birth history, because these may affect feeding ability, growth, and development. The nutritional status of dependent children is also influenced by their caregiver's health, psychosocial environment, cultural practices, and financial status.

The assessment of dietary intake in children reviews past dietary intake, examines factors affecting current intake, determines macronutrient and micronutrient requirements and the ability to meet them, and identifies risks for nutritional problems. Key areas that should be explored include the following:

- appetite, expression of hunger, and satiety
- duration of meals and feeding dynamics between child and caregiver
- feeding ability and tolerance
- appropriateness of infant diet and preparation of infant formula

- use of appropriate food and water safety strategies
- quality of diet and food availability

The risk factors contributing to malnutrition among in-school children in developing countries span across diverse domains. Demographic factors, including low family income, higher socioeconomic status, nuclear or large family sizes, parental unemployment or specific occupational statuses, and educational status of parents, significantly influence the prevalence of malnutrition. Environmental aspects such as the type of residence (rural/urban), household sanitation, and living conditions also play pivotal roles. Knowledge of nutrition, dietary habits, nutrient deficiencies, physical activity levels, and prevailing health conditions further compound the risk. The health impact of malnutrition encompasses a wide array of issues, from compromised general health status and specific nutrient deficiencies to fetal/maternal health and morbidity. Moreover, malnutrition exerts a substantial toll on school performance and attendance, affecting cognitive functions, academic achievements, and overall educational trajectories.

Environmental factors, such as living in flood-prone areas, inadequate sanitation, and lack of access to clean water, are prevalent in many developing regions. These challenges significantly impact children's health, making them more susceptible to diseases that further exacerbate malnutrition. In such contexts, efforts to improve living conditions by providing clean water, sanitation facilities, and safe housing are crucial to combatting malnutrition. Healthcare-related findings underscore systemic issues related to knowledge gaps, inadequate healthcare access, and cultural practices. Insufficient knowledge about proper nutrition and suboptimal breastfeeding practices perpetuate malnutrition. In many cases, limited access to healthcare facilities and health education exacerbates these challenges, indicating a need for accessible and culturally sensitive healthcare interventions.

Dietary habits among in-school children in developing countries reflect both economic constraints and cultural preferences. Food insecurity, dietary monotony, and an inadequate intake of essential nutrients are often rooted in limited access to diverse and nutritious food sources. The lack of dietary diversity is not only a consequence of poverty but also influenced by cultural habits and food availability. Additionally, sedentary lifestyles and limited physical activity among children compound the issue of malnutrition. This stems from various factors, including inadequate infrastructure for recreational activities, safety concerns in outdoor spaces, and a lack of awareness regarding the importance of physical exercise.

Conclusion. The pervasive issue of malnutrition among in-school children in developing countries encompasses a complex interplay of socio-economic, environmental, and health-related factors. These multifaceted risk factors, rooted in poverty, inadequate healthcare access, environmental challenges, and lifestyle dynamics, significantly impact the nutritional status and overall well-being of children. The health implications span from immediate gastrointestinal and respiratory ailments to long-term consequences affecting maternal health, intergenerational health, and cognitive development. Malnutrition's profound impact extends beyond health, detrimentally affecting educational outcomes, including cognitive abilities, academic performance, and school attendance, perpetuating cycles of disadvantage among vulnerable populations. Addressing these challenges demands comprehensive policy measures aligned with the SDGs, advocating for poverty alleviation, nutritional literacy, improved healthcare access, sanitation, and gender equality. Tailored interventions, community-based programs, and collaborative efforts across sectors and international organizations are imperative to mitigate malnutrition's detrimental effects

on in-school children. While this review offers valuable insights, future studies should focus on longitudinal research, interventional studies, and broader inclusivity in populations and languages to deepen our understanding and enhance effective strategies to combat malnutrition among these vulnerable groups. In this study, at least 1/3 of children's energy needs were covered by food provided in 85.71% of schools. None of the schools meet the needs of schoolchildren for micronutrients (iron, vitamin A, vitamin C). Regarding dietary diversity, no significant difference was found between the two groups. No studies have examined the nutritional adequacy of meals served by PNASI kitchens, and this study is the first to do so. The study informs policy makers to review and redesign the National Integrated School Feeding Program. This is the first study to assess the nutritional adequacy of the meals served in the PNASI canteen and their effect on the dietary diversity of schoolchildren. The energy intake from the food offered to schoolchildren and its adequacy are generally acceptable even if in all schools they do not cover 1/3 of children needs, but the content of micronutrients of food offered and their adequacy is very low. The findings suggest that a multi-strategy intervention involving the installation of school gardens supported by nutritional education in primary schools.

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